

Covid and Nutrition: a Machine Learning Perspective

Nafiseh Jafari
Engineering Department,
Qom University,
Qom, Iran
nafisehjafari75@gmail.com

Mohammad Reza Besharati
Department of Computer
Engineering
Sharif University
of Technology
Tehran, Iran
besharati@ce.sharif.edu

Mohammad Izadi
Department of Computer
Engineering
Sharif University
of Technology
Tehran, Iran
izadi@sharif.edu

Alireza Talebpour
Computer Science and
Engineering Department,
Shahid Beheshti University,
Tehran, Iran
talebpour@sbu.ac.ir

Abstract— We gathered somehow big data from a Self-report online questionnaire survey from more than 16000 Iranian Families (residents of 1000 urban and rural points of Iran). The resulting data store has more than 1M data records and more than 1G automatically inferred information records. Based on this data store, we have run some machine learning experiments to investigate the relationship between nutrition and Covid-19 infection risk. With high accuracy scores, our results strongly suggest that the foods and water-sources containing some natural bioactive and phytochemical agents are lowering the risk of apparent infection of Covid-19.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Random Forest, Multilayer Perceptron, Covid-19, Nutrition, Diet, Big-Data

I. INTRODUCTION

Sars-Cov-2 pandemic (Covid-19) is a global crisis that causes serious problems around the world. Many researchers are trying to tackle its different aspects. In the Computer Engineering side of knowledge, Machine Learning is a known method to prepare data-driven insights to the newly born diseases such as Covid-19.

Many aspects of this pandemic are data-oriented: Infection Diagnosis from CT-Scan Image of patients[1][2] or other Symptoms[3], Infection Diagnosis from metabolomics[4] and serologic data[5][6], Epidemiologic analysis[7][8] and Predictions[9], Viral Genetics[10] and host Epigenetics studies[11], Evolutionary Path findings[12], Contact Tracing[13] and Quarantine Enforcing, and many other aspects[14].

Here we have data from our observational study about the relationship between families' dietary nutrition regime and their Covid-19 infection risk status [15]. We gathered somehow big data from a Self-report online questionnaire survey from more than 16000 Iranian Families (residents of 1000 urban and rural points of Iran). The resulting data store has more than 1M data records and more than 1G automatically inferred information records. Based on this data store, we have run some machine learning experiments to investigate the relationship between nutrition and Covid-19 infection risk.

II. THE DATA GATHERING

The data-store mentioned above includes records about Life Style effects (including nutrition, water consumption sources,

physical exercise, Smoking, Age, Gender, Ethnicity, Health and Disease Factors, and many other items) on the status of Covid-19 Infection in families (i.e., residents of a home). These items construct a set of 125 Features (84 features for the Nutrition State of Family). In phase 1, till the last Mordad-Month, 11K filled questionnaires are gathered. After it, in phase 2 till Day-Month, more 5 K-filled questionnaires are added to reach more than 16K available filled questionnaire forms. A subset of our data is available from [16].

III. THE EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

We used Weka as our primary platform on a Corei7 PC. The 20 Experiments show a somehow good accuracy level. Many classification algorithms are served and two of them have better accuracies: Random Forest Algorithm [17] and Multilayer Perceptron [18].

TABLE I. RANDOM FOREST RESULTS WITH 10-FOLD CROSS VALIDATION

Random Forest	Window Size for Running Average (Averaging Filter)	# of Features	# of Instances	# of Classes	Accuracy %	Time (Computational) Complexity
EXP-1	1	9	2540	4	67	20 seconds
EXP-2	20	9	2540	4	47	20 seconds
EXP-3	20	83	16227	4	85.17	2 minutes
EXP-4	20	122	16227	4	86.31	5 minutes
EXP-5	1	125	16227	2	87.39	5 minutes
EXP-6	1	125	16227	4	74.35	5 minutes
EXP-7	20	125	16227	4	86.40	5 minutes
EXP-8	50	125	16227	4	94.33	5 minutes
EXP-9	100	125	16227	4	96.96	5 minutes
EXP-10	200	125	16227	4	98.18	5 minutes
EXP-11	400	125	16227	4	99.04	5 minutes

TABLE II. MULTILAYERED PERCEPTRON RESULTS WITH 10-FOLD CROSS VALIDATION

Multilayer Perceptron	Window Size for Running Average (Averaging Filter)	# of Features	# of Instances	# of Classes	Accuracy %	Time (Computational) Complexity
EXP-12	1	9	2540	4	71*	1 minutes**
EXP-13	20	9	2540	4	37	10 minutes
EXP-14	20	83	16227	4	81.26	2 hours
EXP-15	20	122	16227	4	76.00	3 hours
EXP-16	1	125	16227	2	84.51	3 hours
EXP-17	1	125	16277	4	67.25	3 hours
EXP-18	20	125	16227	4	76.43	3 hours
EXP-19	50	125	16227	4	92.22	3 hours
EXP-20	100	125	16227	4	94.99	3 hours

* Deep Neural Network

** using Colab.research.google.com

Figure 1-Learning Performance vs. Window Size for Running Average (an averaging filter for the inputs)

Figure 2- Histogram with Class-Tag Coloring for Feature 25 (Daily Tea Drinking as a habit in lifestyle)

Figure 3- For 330K Dietary Conditions with reduction effect on the Covid-19 risk, we plot the above diagram for Tehran citizens in our data-set. Each point represents a dietary condition group. Each condition includes four subparts (for instance: Daily Coffee Consumption + Daily Dairy Consumption – Weekly Consumption of Fish Meat – High Consumption of Fast Foods).

Our computations on billions of Permutations of nutrition conditions and dietary regime items, based on data from people’s diet and infection status, show that many diet conditions lower the risks of apparent Covid-19 infection by a 90 percent reduction. Some diet conditions increasing the risks by a factor of 3 or more. Our results suggest that some diets have protective effect for COVID-19 Death Risk (figure 3).

We ran an ID3 algorithm [19] (with 2540 instances of data and with 9 features) on Colab and found a decision tree for some important features with a Gini coefficient 0.5 (figure-4).

Figure 4- ID3 for 2540 instances of data with 9 features.

We are going to detail these findings, data and the explaining model in a detailed research paper in the near future. A digest of some observed results (for phase1 till Mordad-Month for 11000 families) are attached in the appendix.

IV. METABOLITES EXPERIMENTS

Nutrition and lifestyle could affect the metabolite profile of the blood serum. So the analysis of metabolites is another way for investigating the relationship between nutrition and Covid-19. In this section, we used the metabolomics data from a Chinese (Wuhan) study [20]: containing 430 metabolite features for 96 blood tests of 44 persons (including healthy, moderate, severe, and fatal Covid-19 cases). So 96 instances with 430 features were available for investigating the relationship between blood metabolites and the Covid-19 infection status and severity. We have run 4 data experiments (with 10-fold cross-validation) for this section. The results show precision and accuracy scores of about 90% and ROC about 0.99. The resulting decision tree of the J48 algorithm suggests that the key-control-variable of “death” and “survive” in severe Covid-19 cases is the level of T3 thyroid hormone in the blood. It is in conformance with some previous research investigations [21] [22].

TABLE III. METABOLITES DATA EXPERIMENTS RESULTS

	Task	Classification Algorithm	Precision %	Recall %	ROC
EXP-M1	Covid-19 Fatality Prediction	J48	85	78	0.84
EXP-M2	Covid-19 Fatality Prediction	Multilayer Perceptron	90	97	0.989
EXP-M3	Covid-19 Fatality Prediction	Logistic Regression	90	97	0.994

EXP-M4	Covid-19 Fatality Prediction	Random Forest	82	100	0.98
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Figure 5- The resulting decision tree of the J48 algorithm suggests that the key-control-variable of “death” and “survive” in severe Covid-19 cases is the level of T3 thyroid hormone in the blood.

V. COUNTRIES’ DIET EXPERIMENTS

At a broader scope, there are differences between countries’ Nutrition diets and also Covid-19 statistics. Based on the dataset provided by [23], we did some classification experiments. The first 99 highly Covid-infected countries were divided into two classes: 46 countries with high Covid-19 mortality rate and 53 countries with low Covid-19 mortality rate. Then based on 31 nutritional and diet-related features, we ran the classification algorithms with 10-fold cross-validations. The result is provided in the remaining, and it suggests a strong relation between nutritional\diet states of countries and their Covid-19 mortality rates.

TABLE IV. COUNTRIES’ DIET DATA EXPERIMENTS RESULTS

	Task	Classification Algorithm	Window Size for Running Average	Accuracy %
EXP-C1	Covid-19 Mortality Rate Prediction	Random Forest	1	64.65
EXP-C2	Covid-19 Mortality Rate Prediction	Random Forest	10	92.3

VI. CONCLUSION

We conducted a somehow big questionnaire survey from more than 11000 Iranian families (resident in more than 1000 different urban cities and rural points inside IRI) and a somehow big-data “Covid-19 and Life-Style” data-store (with more than 1M data-Records and more than 1G-Items which could be yielded by acquiring semantic entailment rules) was provided from it. This big-data includes records about Life Style effects

(including nutrition, water consumption sources, physical exercise, Smoking, Age, Gender, Health and Disease Factors, and many other items) on the status of Covid-19 Infection in families (i.e., residents of a home). Our results strongly suggest that the foods and water sources containing some natural hypomethylating agents are lowering the risk of apparent infection of Covid-19. Overall, The Data Experiments show a good accuracy level for the relationship between nutrition and Sars-Cov-2 infection. Furthermore, our computations on billions Permutations of nutrition conditions and dietary regime items show that many diet conditions lower the risks of apparent Covid-19 infection.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMNT

We would like to express our special appreciation and best thanks to Prof. Reza Malekzadeh, Dr. Ehsan Mostafavi, Dr. Alireza Ghasempour, Dr. Hossein Shojaei, Dr. Zahra Tarokh, Dr. Navid Rabiee, Dr. Ehsan Shabani, Dr. Hossein Moradi, Dr. Seyyed Hossein Pourhoseini, Dr. Maryam Hourali, Dr. Zahra Besharati, Faculty Staff of QM Research Institute of Shahid Beheshti University, DisysLab members of Sharif University of Technology and 16000 contributing Iranian families in our online questionnaire survey.

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IX. APPENDIX

TABLE V. A DIGEST OF RESULTS

Factor in Family LifeStyle	Observed COVID-19 apparent Infection Risk Change (in %)	Relative Risk ¹ (RR)	Statistical Significance due to 99.9% Confidence Interval	Statistical Significance due to 95% Confidence Interval	Number of Questionnaires
Turmeric	-87	0.45	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Black pepper	-65	0.51	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Islamic Fasting for entire Ramadan	-61	0.55	Yes	Yes	About 10K
Cinnamon	-59	0.55	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Legumes and chickpea	-52	0.55	Yes	Yes	About 5K
Dark chocolate, dark cocoa	-50	0.54	Yes	Yes	About 5K
Bell pepper	-48	0.59	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Tea	-48	0.66	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Sea salt	-48	0.57	Yes	Yes	About 10K
Vitamin D or Multivitamin Tablets	-46	0.62	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Walnuts or Nuts	-46	0.62	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Consuming Rose Water Once a Few Days In Food Or Drink	-46	0.60	No	Yes	About 5K
High consumption of apple juice or apple	-14	0.86	No	No	About 5K
Home water purification devices	21	1.23	No	Yes	More Than 11K
High consumption of deep frying or fried foods	24	1.25	No	Yes	More Than 11K
Soft drinks and soda	24	1.25	No	No	About 3K
High consumption of sugar	26	1.27	No	No	About 3K
Monthly consumption of fish meat or seafood	27	1.31	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Weekly consumption of fish meat or seafood	28	1.30	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
High consumption of sweet pepper (not bell pepper, excluding bell pepper)	37	1.37	No	Yes	About 10K
Eat fish meat or seafood once every two or three days	42	1.44	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
High consumption of fast food	45	1.46	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Pumpkin	49	1.5	No	Yes	About 3K
Sugar substitutes, artificial sweeteners	60	1.62	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Fruits natural products: Grape Syrup	-45	0.61	Yes	Yes	About 5K
Daily yogurt consumption	-45	0.64	Yes	Yes	About 10K
Tahini and natural products like it	-44	0.61	Yes	Yes	About 10K
Low or controlled consumption of oil	-44	0.62	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Consume Courgette once every ten days	-44	0.59	Yes	Yes	about 5K
Garlic	-42	0.65	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Consume Eggplant once every ten days	-42	0.64	Yes	Yes	about 5K
High consumption of fruits and vegetables	-41	0.67	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Natural Honey	-41	0.67	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Green pea	-38	0.63	No	No	About 5K
Ginger	-36	0.68	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Fruits natural products: fruit-roll	-35	0.67	Yes	Yes	About 10K
Local dairy products	-33	0.71	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Daily coffee consumption	-33	0.69	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Traditional breads (whole-wheat flour)	-32	0.71	Yes	Yes	More Than 11K
Soybean and its products	-32	0.70	No	Yes	About 5K
Head Cabbage	-31	0.69	No	Yes	About 10K
Islamic fasting, once a week	-31	0.69	No	No	About 10K
Vegetarian diet	-29	0.71	No	No	About 10K
Probiotic dairy products	-25	0.76	No	Yes	More Than 11K
Slimming weight loss diet or low-calorie diet	-24	0.77	No	No	About 10K
Non-alcoholic beer	-21	0.79	No	No	About 5K
Physical exercise and walking	-19	0.82	No	Yes	More Than 11K
Tobacco and smoking	-15	0.86	No	No	More Than 11K